

Dendrochronological and anatomical analysis of wood from Dannevirke, Schleswig.

Aoife Daly, Ph.d.
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and Frauke Witte, Museum Sønderjylland - Haderslev

A total of 56 samples from wood found during excavations at Dannevirke, Schleswig were submitted for analysis. The main purpose of this analysis was to identify samples that were suitable for dendrochronological dating, by locating oak samples containing more than 50 rings. Twenty of the samples fulfilled these criteria and were analysed dendrochronologically. The remaining 36 samples were examined microscopically to ascertain their wood genus, tree-age and form. Subsequently, wooden artefacts from the excavation were examined, with a view to attempting non-invasive dendrochronological analysis. Of the artefacts three spades, a wooden mallet and a single plank were analysed dendrochronologically while the wood anatomy of the remaining were examined.

Fig. 1. Dannevirke. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated oak samples from the 12th century phase. The timbers are possibly re-used from an earlier structure. The posts might indicate the dating for the context in which the wood was situated c. AD 1189-1204 (marked in green).

Immature (short-lived) structural wood

The large majority of the samples are of oak and while many might be from full round branches or young trees, they are too eroded to allow intact bark edge to be preserved. One sample had bark preserved but the sapwood just under the bark was not preserved enough to allow ring measurement. It was chosen therefore not to carry out tree-ring studies of this short-lived material. The ring count of these short-lived samples are therefore an indication of the minimum age of the trees or

branches used. The results of the examination of the short-lived material is listed in table 5. As mentioned, oak dominates the material with 29 pieces and to that can be added the longer-lived material that is analysed dendrochronologically (see catalogue). Willow is the next most frequent wood genus, but is represented by just four pieces. The average minimum age of the trees is 21 years.

		DE060039	DE06013a	DE06012a	DE060019	DE06014a	DE06016a	DE06015a	DE06008b	DE060029	DE060199	DE06007a	DE06009a
DE06_timbers&posts 12thC	DE060039	*	-	2,45	-	-	1,37	\	\	1,86	2,75	-	1,37
	DE06013a	-	*	2,71	1,01	-	4,64	\	\	1,82	2,05	2,86	2,7
	DE06012a	2,45	2,71	*	3,04	1,7	3,57	\	\	-	1,01	-	-
	DE060019	-	1,01	3,04	*	3,47	2,75	\	\	2,2	1,48	-	2,44
	DE06014a	-	-	1,7	3,47	*	3,58	2,87	-	-	1,08	-	1,07
	DE06016a	1,37	4,64	3,57	2,75	3,58	*	5,54	-	3,76	2,11	2,67	2,6
	DE06015a	\	\	\	\	2,87	5,54	*	1,66	4,37	1,99	2,56	3,1
	DE06008b	\	\	\	\	-	-	1,66	*	3,32	3,18	4,13	2,91
	DE060029	1,86	1,82	-	2,2	-	3,76	4,37	3,32	*	4,85	4,85	4,53
	DE060199	2,75	2,05	1,01	1,48	1,08	2,11	1,99	3,18	4,85	*	3,34	4,19
	DE06007a	-	2,86	-	-	-	2,67	2,56	4,13	4,85	3,34	*	4,24
	DE06009a	1,37	2,7	-	2,44	1,07	2,6	3,1	2,91	4,53	4,19	4,24	*

Table 1. Dannevirke. The correlation between the tree-ring curves from the 12th century oak samples from the site. The grey tone highlights the high t-values.

Mature (long-lived) structural wood

The long-lived wood was selected for dendrochronological analysis. All samples are of oak. Of the 20 samples analysed, 14 are dated (fig. 3).

12th century material

The majority of the material is dating to the 12th century, but this material forms two groups – large timbers and smaller posts. The larger timbers (fig. 2) show indications of weathering suggesting that they had been exposed in an earlier structure, and that their find context therefore represents secondary usage. Of the six dated timbers, one (154 DE06016a) has sapwood preserved. Allowing for missing sapwood the tree that this sample comes from was felled in c. AD 1153-68. One of the timbers represents a later felling event however. Sample 155 (DE06015a) has no sapwood preserved, and comes from a tree felled after AD 1173 (marked in blue in fig. 1). Five posts form a second group and this group is shown using green shading in figs. 1 and 3 and in table 1. One of these posts has sapwood preserved, and is from a tree that was felled in c. AD 1189-1204. The results for the other posts indicate that these might also be from the same felling event (marked in green in fig. 1). A single post was made from a much longer-lived tree, and does not exhibit very high correlation with the posts and timbers from this

dated material (table 1). This post might represent a separate felling event – after AD 1147 (marked in pink in fig. 1). The latest felling event in the 12th century material as a whole takes place in around 1189-1204 (green in the diagrams). The context in which these were found must have been deposited on or after this time. The tree-ring curves from the 12th century material is averaged to form an average curve (DE06_timbers&posts 12thC) of 171 years in length. As the table of correlation between this average and diverse tree-ring datasets for Northern Europe indicates (table 2), the oaks for the structures preserved here had probably grown locally.

Fig. 2. Dannevirke. The timbers from the 12th century phase.

Filenames	-	-	DE06_timbers & posts 12thC	
-	start	dates	AD1008	
-	dates	end	AD1178	
5100m002	AD988	AD1209	6,12	Lykkegård (Eriksen pers comm)
three 12th	AD903	AD1260	5,08	DK Three 12thC S. Jutland ships (Daly unpubl.)
DM100003	AD436	AD1968	5,07	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni.)
9M456781	109BC	AD1986	4,86	Jylland/Fyn (Nationalmuseet)
G351WZ01	AD1084	AD1354	4,86	Suderburg (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
60873M01	AD982	AD1188	4,63	Kolding cog 11 timbers (Daly 2015)
RIBEZ001	AD907	AD1206	4,62	Ribe (Daly unpubl.)
5069M001	AD944	AD1163	4,54	Løgumgårde 20 timbers (Daly 1999)
CD51JZ01	AD929	AD1234	4,49	Møllestrømmen 23 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
4M000001	AD1058	AD1350	4,47	Danmark Svendborg (Nationalmuseet)
0099M003	AD1004	AD1205	4,19	Møllestrømmen skib (Daly 2015)
G370FZ03	AD1118	AD1231	4,17	Oldenburg (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)

Table 2. Dannevirke. The correlation between the site chronology for the 12th century timber from the site and a selection of chronologies for oak from Northern Europe. The grey tone highlights the high t-values. The source of each chronology is given.

Filenames	-	-	DE06M003	
-	start	dates	AD512	
-	dates	end	AD677	
DM100003	AD436	AD1968	12,45	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni.)
X005M001	AD526	AD737	8,84	Reesholm Schlei Schleswig 9 timbers (Daly 2014)
CD501Z01	AD551	AD806	8,35	Padborg Søndermose 4 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
H11CMM01	AD550	AD815	7,97	Haithabu-Siedlung 18 timbers (Hamburg Uni., revised Daly 2007)
9M456781	109BC	AD1986	7,64	Jylland/Fyn (Nationalmuseet)
DM100008	AD457	AD1723	7,31	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni.)
H11E9M01	AD501	AD728	7,19	Danewerk 2 timbers (Hamburg Uni., revised Daly 2007)
G370IZ01	AD482	AD692	6,61	Oldorf (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
CD701Z02	AD487	AD963	6,17	Vorbasse 46 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
7029M001	AD529	AD833	6,10	Nybro/Søvig bæk 44 timbers (Daly 1999)
F0101M01	AD569	AD898	5,72	Viuf Vesterby brønd/vogn 2 timbers (Daly 2008)
D007M001	AD551	AD837	5,65	Hjulby, Fyn (Daly 2009)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	5,49	Sjælland (Daly unpubl.)
DM200004	30BC	AD1960	5,45	G WESER (Göttingen Uni.)
F0101M02	AD524	AD898	5,36	Viuf Vesterby 9 timbers (Daly 2008)
DMML003A	6069BC	AD928	5,35	Moseeg; Ost-NDS (Leuschner pers comm)
H11CKM01	AD550	AD887	5,28	Haithabu-Siedlung 75 timbers (Hamburg Uni., revised Daly 2007)
2128M001	AD452	AD881	5,24	Næs, Sjælland (Daly 2000)

Table 3. Dannevirke. The correlation between the tree-ring averages of the 7th century timber from the site and a selection of chronologies for oak from Northern Europe. The grey tone highlights the high t-values. The source of each chronology is given.

7th century material

Three dated samples represent 7th century activity at Dannevirke. Two samples are from structural wood while a third was sampled from a fragment of a plank artefact. None of these samples had sapwood preserved. Sample 227 (DE060069) is from a ditch at Dannevirke. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for this timber is estimated to be after c. AD 685. Sample 257 (DE061108) is from the plank. This plank fragment was found in the same context as a large wooden mallet (described below). The plank also only has heartwood preserved, and is from a tree

that was felled after c. AD 693. These three late 7th century timbers might belong to the same felling phase, marked in orange in fig. 3 – after c. AD 693. The tree-ring curves from the three samples are averaged to form a curve (DE06M003) of 166 years in length. As the table of correlation between this average and diverse tree-ring datasets for oak from Northern Europe indicates (table 3), the oaks for this phase probably grew locally.

Fig. 3. Dannevirke. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated oak samples along with the C14 dated oak artefacts. The coloured shading indicated the probable phases that are represented in the material.

The artefacts

Twelve wooden artefacts were examined on the 11th March 2015 by the author, with a view to attempting non-invasive dendrochronological analysis. One artefact was a plank fragment, so this was sampled for conventional analysis, and is described above. The remaining artefacts consist of complete or fragments of nine spades, a wooden mallet and a perforated board. The objects were examined first to assess their potential for dendrochronology (wood genus and number of rings) and then to their suitability for non-invasive measurement. Non-invasive measurement, by taking a series of macro photos of the wood surface and measuring from the photos, is possible in some circumstances, particularly in the case of art-historical objects like painted panels and church sculpture, when the tree-rings are readily visible on the surface of the object (for example Daly 2014). It was found that three of the artefacts were not oak, and that just four of the oak objects contained potentially enough rings for dendrochronological dating.

Spade 187

This spade is shown in fig. 4, illustrating the process of photographing for tree-ring analysis. The spade seems to be incomplete, discarded when it broke during

manufacture (Frauke Witte pers comm). Perhaps therefore, the surface of the object has not been subject to wear and tear, and this is probably why it has been possible to attain tree-ring measurements on the longitudinal section (see fig. 6) without cutting. The spade contains 114 tree-rings. A possible cross-match was provisionally seen, but this was not replicated to allow confident dating of the tree-ring curve. Therefore, it was necessary to suggest C14 dating of the spade to be carried out. Two samples, one from the innermost preserved ring and a second sample from the outermost preserved ring were extracted and submitted to Beta Analytic for C14 analysis. Two samples were extracted to optimise the calibration of the C14 dating, utilising the so-called 'wiggly match' method (Galimberti et al 2004).

As we know the exact number of rings that are present between the inner sampled ring and the outer (114 tree-rings/years) the results of the C14 analysis of these two can be calibrated together using OxCal (v4.2.4) <https://c14.arch.ox.ac.uk/oxcal/OxCal.html> (accessed 22nd February 2016) (see Bronk Ramsey 2009; Bronk Ramsey & Lee 2013 & Bronk Ramsey et al 2001). To identify the probable felling date for the tree used to make the spade we also must allow for missing sapwood. The tree from which the spade was made was probably felled after AD 661-709 (fig. 5). The context in which this spade fragment was found seems to belong to the later 7th or early 8th century AD.

Fig. 4. Dannevirke. Macro photographs are taken of the preserved longitudinal surface of spade 187 to carry out non-invasive measurement of the tree-rings for dendrochronological analysis.

Name	Unmodelled (BC/AD)			Modelled (BC/AD)			Indices				Select	Page break	
	from	to	%	from	to	%	A _{comb}	A	L	P			C
Show all Show structure												All Visible	
▼ D_Sequence Dannevirke spade 187	661	709	95.4				88.4					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date Beta 430994	436	643	95.5	531	579	95.4		84.3				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/>
R_Date Beta 430995	609	687	95.4	646	694	95.4		99.8				<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/>
P3 Felling date				661	709	95.4						<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/>

Fig. 5. Dannevirke. The result of the modelled calibration of the C14 dates from spade 187. The estimated felling for the tree can be placed at after c. AD 661-709 (95.4% probability).

Fig. 6. Dannevirke. Spade 187. Macro photo of the flat surface of the spade, where the longitudinal section of the oak anatomy can be seen. A ruler is used to calibrate the photograph prior to tree-ring measurement.

Artefact 234

A fragment of a perforated oak board is found in the same context as the above mentioned spade (187). It was assessed as to the potential for non-invasive dendrochronological analysis. Macro photos of the end-grain were taken, and while it is possible to ascertain that the object contains c. 50 rings, the clarity of the rings due to the softness of the wood surface did not allow reliable measurement. A single sample was taken for C14, from a ring in the sapwood. The calibrated result of the analysis (95% probability) places the date of the sample from the board at Cal AD 650 to 690, Cal AD 750 to 760. This is a very wide margin, but would agree with the result of the C14 analysis of spade 187 which places the artefacts at the end of the 7th century AD.

Spade 198

This spade fragment is not of oak. A smaller fragment was taken for wood anatomy, and it is found on examination to be *Fagus sp.*, beech. From the macro photos it can be estimated that this spade fragment contains around 130 rings but the rings are not clear enough to ensure reliable measurement.

Spade 205

This spade is not very wide, and it was not examined in detail. It is probably oak, and it probably contains too few rings for dendrochronological analysis so it was not included in this analysis.

Spade 240

This spade is preserved to its full length. The spade is narrow, with a broadening at the top (fig. 8) and is fashioned with a foot-rest (fig. 7). It is made of oak. From the wood anatomy it can be seen that the spade is probably fashioned from branch wood or a very young sapling, and that the foot-rest is carved out of a branch that protruded almost perpendicular to the main stem. Spade 240 contained no more than around 25 tree-rings.

Fig. 7. Dannevirke. Spade 240 is of oak, but contained too few rings for dendrochronological analysis. It was observed that the foot-rest of this spade is fashioned from a branch that protruded from the main stem.

Fig. 8. Dannevirke. Spade 240 is of oak, but contained too few rings for dendrochronological analysis.

Spade 246

The full blade portion of spade 246 is preserved. It is oak and contains 82 rings, all heartwood. The rings were clearly visible on the spade surface, so non-invasive measurement was possible. Unfortunately however, the tree-ring curve from this spade could not be dated.

Spade 263

This spade is of oak and its narrow blade is well preserved (fig. 9). The spade contains just c. 25 tree-rings.

Fig. 9. Dannevirke. Spade 263 is of oak, but contained too few rings for dendrochronological analysis.

Spade 266

Spade fragment 266 is not oak. A very small fragment was taken for wood-anatomical analysis, to identify the wood genus. It is found that the spade is made from *Alnus sp.*, alder.

Spade 267

The spade fragment 267 is not oak either. Again a fragment was taken for identification and this piece is also found to be of *Alnus sp.*, alder.

Spade 318

Artefact 318 is a rather narrow spade made of oak (fig. 10). The tree-rings are visible in longitudinal section, on the blade surface, and macro photos of these, as well as of the end-grain at the top of the spade handle were taken. A series of 70 rings were measured from the longitudinal section, but the measurements were not wholly confident, due to lack of clarity of the rings at places. The spade is therefore not dated.

Artefact 268

This artefact is a large mallet or club, roughly hewn from a whole log (fig. 11). The tree-rings visible at the hewn end show irregular growth, with phases of fast and phases of very slow growth. A series of 60 rings proved possible to measure, from the macro photos of the end-grain, but the irregularity of the series, and the quite short length means that this mallet could not be dated. This mallet was found in the same context as the plank fragment discussed above (Astrid Tummuscheit pers

comm), dating to the late 7th century AD. A C14 sample was taken from the outermost ring of the mallet, just under the preserved bark. The calibrated date for this sample gives a range Cal AD 1155 to 1255. The mallet possibly represents a later intrusion into the 7th century structure.

Fig. 10. Dannevirke. Spade 318 is of oak. It contained 70 rings, but could not be dated.

Fig. 11. Dannevirke. Mallet 268 is of oak. It is fashioned roughly from a full log of a c. 60 year-old tree/branch. It could not be dated

In the interest of open access to data and to enable researchers to utilise this material in the future, the measurements are printed in the catalogue. All measurements will also be submitted to the Digital Collaboratory for Cultural Dendrochronology (DCCD, www.dendrochronology.eu). For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t-value ("t-test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed. For the wood identification, an identification key developed by Schweingruber (1990) is consulted. To estimate the felling date of the trees that the dated samples come from, a sapwood estimate for Northern Germany, which suggests c. 20 (-5 +10) sapwood years in oaks, is applied here (Hollstein 1980).

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Sample no.	Wood genus	Common name	No. of rings	Diameter (mm)	Conversion/comment
2014.130.177	<i>Prunus sp.</i>	Stone fruits	5	100	round
2014.130.175	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	20	160	half
2014.130.142	<i>Salix sp.</i>	Willow	10-15	98	round
2014.130.107	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 15	c. 80	round
2014.130.231	<i>Salix sp.</i>	Willow	c. 10-15	c. 180	quarter
2014.130.135	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 36	160	round? eroded
2014.130.224	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	20	135	branch wood?
2014.130.110	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	17	95	round
2014.130.109	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	19	?	very eroded
2014.130.235	<i>Alnus sp.</i>	Alder	c. 22	90	round
2014.130.127	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	24	75	round? eroded
2014.130.112	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	10-20	70	round? eroded
2014.130.140	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	18	80	round? eroded
2014.130.119	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	26	c. 100	quarter
2014.130.114	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	16	75	other
2014.130.139	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	17	85	other
2014.130.144	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	17	c. 120	other
2014.130.104	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	27	c. 110	quarter
2014.130.180	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	?	?	?
2014.130.230	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	25	92	one side round, other squared
2014.130.156	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 18	95	eroded round?
2014.130.117	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 22	78	eroded half/quarter
2014.130.237	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	10	170	eroded branching section
2014.130.243	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 33	255	eroded whole log?
2014.130.115	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 15	90	trimmed round
2014.130.258	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	40	150	squared (fragment?)
2014.130.236	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	11	95	round but no sapwood (eroded?)
2014.130.244	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	23	110	round (to bark?)
2014.130.113	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	36	110	round to bark
2014.130.106	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 20	68	eroded originally round (?)
2014.130.118	<i>Salix sp.</i>	Willow	> 6	130	eroded
2014.130.157	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 30	100	eroded
2014.130.269	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 25	120	squared?
2014.130.226	<i>Quercus sp.</i>	Oak	c. 14	265	eroded (branched?)
2014.130.120	<i>Salix sp.</i>	Willow	c. 10-15	102	eroded
2014.130.245	<i>Corylus sp.</i>	Hazel	c. 50	125	round

Table 5. Dannevirke. List of results of the anatomical analysis of the short-lived wood from the site.

Catalogue

Catalogue format:

Filename
Title and sample number
Tree species (QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak, PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine, PCAB = <i>Picea abies</i> , spruce) and number of years measured
Chronological position of the tree-ring curve
Number of sapwood years, presence of bark
Felling date
The measurements start at the innermost preserved ring

DE060019
Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.153
Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 71 years length
Dated AD1058 to AD1128
0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
Average ring width 181.23 Sensitivity 0.19
Interpretation after AD1143
298 189 205 276 262 324 319 342 198 150
110 101 123 131 86 85 93 123 117 114
161 196 141 124 169 178 98 123 144 120
122 122 127 142 183 266 279 239 191 203
180 183 217 225 180 181 193 238 220 170
251 232 257 249 210 240 194 158 235 180
143 158 166 115 142 184 134 172 107 211
168

DE060029
Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.129
Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 81 years length
Dated AD1081 to AD1161
0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
Average ring width 81.35 Sensitivity 0.16
Interpretation after AD1176
175 159 156 145 139 104 81 59 49 42
47 42 61 66 87 92 120 90 86 137
134 71 79 92 99 90 81 99 109 87
65 80 75 72 68 75 95 104 90 102
102 71 105 112 88 52 68 65 49 42
42 46 44 36 35 41 42 32 37 50
46 43 47 42 51 48 64 58 86 68
73 77 123 113 111 117 107 95 100 125
132

DE060039
Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.134
Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 125 years length
Dated AD1008 to AD1132
0 sapwood rings and no bark surface
Average ring width 41.44 Sensitivity 0.18
Interpretation after AD1147
59 78 52 44 47 47 66 72 65 58
44 34 30 30 40 32 30 27 20 20
18 23 27 24 39 47 75 70 66 90
61 47 67 67 81 45 40 49 47 26
28 30 32 32 22 22 24 26 23 37
35 44 35 32 45 34 30 28 37 49
41 39 35 28 36 32 32 45 44 35
30 24 32 47 38 30 31 38 57 40
45 44 25 24 27 32 30 33 28 36
29 38 50 26 28 32 28 40 27 25
27 27 29 28 28 32 34 39 37 46
46 53 57 40 42 50 51 48 39 69
77 75 128 76 72

DE060049

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.111

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 27 years length

Undated

2 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 172.11 Sensitivity 0.22

107	162	176	216	154	187	204	154	84	192
176	173	145	261	249	208	199	223	220	191
140	171	144	178	137	113	83			

DE06005a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.173

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 55 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings but possible h/s boundary

Average ring width 183.58 Sensitivity 0.22

243	223	315	250	182	200	260	245	237	219
246	218	156	299	283	256	170	216	135	97
74	170	172	156	135	211	186	182	204	153
248	209	189	215	200	141	288	112	123	160
197	178	195	222	171	133	140	129	91	131
140	99	92	104	97					

DE060069

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.227

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 150 years length

Dated AD516 to AD665

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 73.52 Sensitivity 0.19

Interpretation after AD685

171	174	134	162	134	104	123	126	201	164
177	169	126	84	99	99	92	162	117	115
86	149	54	51	63	57	61	88	91	99
91	76	95	81	67	71	50	52	47	61
72	53	59	94	55	46	43	64	95	80
65	71	79	88	70	44	66	60	49	41
55	97	113	94	105	72	94	50	81	104
76	79	81	91	99	64	56	79	97	106
114	116	92	65	82	101	77	43	59	60
78	94	103	78	62	76	67	83	80	77
83	72	63	47	42	68	78	94	85	81
63	52	54	76	76	65	68	53	48	49
40	34	29	33	29	30	30	34	30	29
22	25	33	42	34	30	25	28	36	35
27	24	32	34	29	26	21	24	25	24

DE06007a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.206

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 83 years length

Dated AD1086 to AD1168

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 69.69 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation after AD1183

101	91	79	67	57	64	67	80	60	57
43	50	41	55	64	57	40	48	85	79
68	73	73	107	69	67	71	74	63	63
59	50	62	38	40	56	47	49	48	46
44	48	46	31	32	34	54	79	62	94
110	105	69	91	108	113	70	70	79	105
110	47	51	64	79	64	81	94	85	85
78	88	64	79	125	129	79	91	92	90
62	46	49							

DE06008b

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.126

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 59 years length

Dated AD1105 to AD1163

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 107.90 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation after AD1178

129	72	94	143	164	121	102	96	62	61
78	85	74	137	83	126	131	131	144	94
100	75	107	104	82	87	58	87	80	95
103	116	101	80	90	142	109	134	145	127
143	161	133	132	135	116	122	123	127	107
107	100	129	104	91	103	106	86	92	

DE06009a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.131

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 52 years length

Dated AD1085 to AD1136

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 91.31 Sensitivity 0.20

Interpretation after AD1152

227	129	61	66	82	78	81	116	96	88
79	87	112	149	128	160	140	85	78	110
109	84	73	100	135	63	65	81	84	60
74	66	82	75	75	100	87	88	121	95
96	69	103	108	83	55	58	68	65	64
58	52								

DE06010a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.132

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 66 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings but possible h/s boundary

Average ring width 60.76 Sensitivity 0.21

26	24	23	23	22	32	37	45	38	27
32	23	17	16	14	16	15	15	18	18
22	22	23	17	18	18	24	24	30	53
45	49	41	90	105	140	58	73	96	74
47	59	116	104	49	74	86	123	119	139
119	114	116	105	90	109	93	148	134	148
80	88	74	60	54	59				

DE06011a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.214

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 50 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 117.16 Sensitivity 0.30

95	173	79	41	90	193	148	216	188	289
269	144	117	59	74	113	155	113	126	83
109	123	139	72	82	93	95	74	106	112
125	125	147	175	127	82	112	88	96	64
110	122	134	92	106	66	78	63	80	96

DE06012a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.149

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 121 years length

Dated AD1009 to AD1129

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 135.93 Sensitivity 0.30

Interpretation after AD1150

162	236	135	218	143	161	148	82	114	109
194	163	73	87	139	70	187	113	101	56
129	143	107	87	88	75	68	72	140	82
98	92	80	67	41	42	32	49	70	87
144	175	120	151	82	106	105	136	86	90
94	75	57	44	63	60	65	60	67	61
51	32	36	33	47	50	49	44	52	108
133	127	181	166	181	91	53	152	175	136
141	139	249	319	286	201	248	315	260	145
178	193	95	119	183	250	188	200	105	183
148	192	314	305	332	311	162	190	180	254
206	261	94	176	193	78	124	67	201	267
317									

DE06013a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.150

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 65 years length

Dated AD1060 to AD1124

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 307.35 Sensitivity 0.21

Interpretation after AD1140

248	446	312	479	475	485	285	297	346	358
247	408	374	549	364	424	480	384	500	392
416	384	356	454	460	319	453	212	214	174
184	212	282	354	324	235	286	192	241	310
347	300	239	336	354	314	277	201	295	227
231	255	247	282	227	228	153	190	201	172
198	220	164	230	175					

DE06014a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.157

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 60 years length

Dated AD1080 to AD1139

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 224.03 Sensitivity 0.14

Interpretation after AD1155

209	222	234	319	281	255	319	344	319	322
252	252	251	305	275	220	230	246	194	234
168	181	167	194	237	252	258	246	237	238
258	254	263	280	187	206	267	229	171	256
250	228	220	216	205	189	190	264	186	208
165	171	260	210	122	103	81	93	106	143

DE06015a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.155

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 55 years length

Dated AD1104 to AD1158

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 256.95 Sensitivity 0.22

Interpretation after AD1173

408	447	445	413	305	253	163	170	170	220
174	153	188	237	265	236	275	233	258	358
292	173	171	248	248	186	186	190	337	277
227	191	151	167	139	207	285	311	231	319
264	376	253	324	256	379	273	202	297	291
190	308	265	316	231					

DE06016a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.154

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 67 years length

Dated AD1072 to AD1138

0 sapwood rings but possible h/s boundary

Average ring width 236.91 Sensitivity 0.22

Interpretation AD1153-68

275	277	174	242	267	209	239	268	272	259
300	286	221	152	235	180	93	128	198	267
251	371	374	335	290	207	152	215	282	219
136	227	345	248	256	236	259	296	226	291
299	310	226	209	217	218	269	261	281	239
211	314	257	187	173	255	229	226	208	268
426	319	215	90	68	78	62			

DE06017a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.233

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 72 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 204.13 Sensitivity 0.23

580	476	368	418	307	379	274	262	342	301
162	297	233	214	256	202	207	168	179	136
92	132	85	165	186	195	142	138	288	219
268	185	139	186	218	121	181	231	209	214
181	190	216	151	159	173	122	125	150	170
238	129	135	153	183	218	179	206	142	115
106	270	282	185	151	157	153	133	137	170
174	89								

DE06018a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.260

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 70 years length

Dated AD512 to AD581

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 157.06 Sensitivity 0.28

Interpretation after AD596

281	311	299	362	481	278	416	442	343	185
94	151	297	360	350	336	270	134	187	240
128	216	163	201	128	168	73	44	35	39
49	54	109	126	162	145	137	136	123	104
121	101	84	86	101	101	105	141	127	69
75	108	93	51	53	73	132	148	123	98
136	121	76	36	78	66	92	74	83	85

DE060199

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.116

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 94 years length

Dated AD1085 to AD1178

4 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 68.83 Sensitivity 0.18

Interpretation AD1189-1204

207	125	111	139	125	83	96	74	84	87
101	99	144	159	137	180	153	91	122	114
101	50	61	54	41	37	36	41	43	37
47	42	45	66	67	88	93	82	119	109
83	50	70	69	51	46	46	58	42	37
37	31	27	24	38	34	32	37	41	31
34	45	45	43	51	60	75	54	71	60
69	64	62	45	50	64	64	55	52	53
59	35	45	53	44	42	48	54	62	92
75	73	50	48						

DE06020a

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.108

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 46 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 96.83 Sensitivity 0.25

61	86	81	93	77	37	29	19	15	13
13	11	12	17	22	15	14	20	57	53
59	60	53	125	145	128	166	109	189	190
167	121	119	121	154	113	146	162	126	105
143	169	247	174	243	175				

DE061019

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg spade SH-2014-130.187

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 114 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 230.41 Sensitivity 0.15

234	288	226	155	247	246	175	164	286	310
321	259	293	285	235	253	303	431	414	440
380	338	343	325	306	237	211	324	315	290
289	322	376	279	226	273	256	248	225	263
192	195	225	271	251	327	207	186	169	249
268	245	212	243	223	279	197	200	228	248
266	279	235	204	212	225	174	235	238	220
250	261	253	210	186	123	130	161	202	219
136	158	171	176	213	227	177	235	269	232
181	221	148	143	146	170	144	163	171	179
175	136	150	163	150	158	183	161	150	211
186	181	139	175						

DE061029

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg spade SH-2014-130.246

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 82 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 181.01 Sensitivity 0.18

184	265	336	269	256	277	241	199	297	281
257	277	248	338	207	211	241	298	286	264
304	256	207	282	235	263	214	123	164	195
158	157	169	172	161	153	153	139	95	139
184	152	163	126	152	133	144	123	182	181
187	199	164	124	170	124	132	186	201	174
170	207	169	137	120	154	160	93	140	111
94	104	142	98	86	104	112	89	79	102
92	108								

DE061038

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg club mallet SH-2014-130.268

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 60 years length

Undated

10 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 92.70 Sensitivity 0.23

97	129	111	140	150	169	260	245	119	102
96	80	121	137	121	88	91	95	113	97
86	80	65	52	72	75	95	103	91	79
88	68	62	68	65	59	91	41	33	66
110	77	40	52	32	33	27	24	23	22
54	86	127	186	190	127	95	80	93	84

DE061048

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg spade SH-2014-130.318

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 70 years length

Undated

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 78.01 Sensitivity 0.18

59	59	64	57	59	74	56	92	113	77
76	79	59	47	50	87	73	85	99	110
90	59	64	82	75	83	72	95	95	95
71	76	155	105	94	99	107	97	92	122
107	99	81	95	80	76	80	94	94	92
100	95	87	73	46	43	60	49	59	66
51	45	37	44	74	66	51	41	82	91

DE061108

Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.257 plank

Raw Ring-width QUSP data of 95 years length

Dated AD583 to AD677

0 sapwood rings and no bark surface

Average ring width 165.58 Sensitivity 0.25

Interpretation after AD693

185	225	368	256	197	230	290	221	133	124
140	158	133	175	158	181	78	89	133	138
125	162	157	173	164	161	91	99	151	101
149	169	178	186	182	176	164	117	223	203
194	171	141	139	129	148	165	143	165	199
181	155	118	76	175	261	193	155	193	111
120	155	132	82	229	166	142	167	194	144
173	261	174	93	130	232	154	146	178	149
214	216	228	165	286	151	135	125	91	135
208	144	152	134	170					

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	Conversion	pith	sapwood	bark?	extra start	extra end	Interpretation / felling
Wood & timber											
DE060019	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.153	71	AD1058	AD1128	O	C	0	N	N	N	after AD1143
DE060029	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.129	81	AD1081	AD1161	W	C	0	N	N	N	after AD1176
DE060039	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.134	125	AD1008	AD1132	W	C	0	N	N	N	after AD1147
DE060049	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.111	27			W	C	2	N	N	S2	undated
DE06005a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.173	55			O	G	0	?	N	N	undated
DE060069	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.227	150	AD516	AD665	O	G	0	N	N	H5	after AD685
DE06007a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.206	83	AD1086	AD1168	O	V	0	N	N	N	after AD1183
DE06008b	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.126	59	AD1105	AD1163	O	V	0	N	N	N	after AD1178
DE06009a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.131	52	AD1085	AD1136	O	C	0	N	N	H1	after AD1152
DE06010a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.132	66			O	G	0	?	N	N	undated
DE06011a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.214	50			O	F	0	N	N	N	undated
DE06012a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.149	121	AD1009	AD1129	O	G	0	N	N	H6	after AD1150
DE06013a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.150	65	AD1060	AD1124	O	G	0	N	N	H1	after AD1140
DE06014a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.157	60	AD1080	AD1139	O	F	0	N	N	H1	after AD1155
DE06015a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.155	55	AD1104	AD1158	O	G	0	N	N	N	after AD1173
DE06016a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.154	67	AD1072	AD1138	O	G	0	?	N	S10	AD1153-68
DE06017a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.233	72			O	C	0	N	N	N	undated
DE06018a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.260	70	AD512	AD581	O	C	0	N	N	N	after AD596
DE060199	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.116	94	AD1085	AD1178	W	C	4	N	N	N	AD1189-1204
DE06020a	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.108	46			W	C	0	N	N	N	undated
Spades etc											
DE061019	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg spade SH-2014-130.187	114			R	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
DE061029	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg spade SH-2014-130.246	82			O	G	0	N	H1	H1	undated
DE061038	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg club mallet SH-2014-130.268	60			?	F	10	N	N	N	undated
DE061048	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg spade SH-2014-130.318	70			O	G	0	N	N	N	undated
DE061108	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130.257 plank	95	AD583	AD677	R	G	0	N	H1	H1	after AD693
Averages											
DE06_timbers&posts 12thC	DE06_timbers&posts 12thC 12 timber mean	171	AD1008	AD1178							
DE06_timbers	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg 1 13 14 15 16 5 timber mean	101	AD1058	AD1158							
DE06002&7&8&9&19	DE06002&7&8&9&19 5 timber mean	98	AD1081	AD1178							
DE06M003	Danneverk LA85 Kr Schleswig-Flensburg SH-2014-130 3 timber meanmean	166	AD512	AD677							
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			22 April 2015								